

UTILIZATION OF MAGNETIZED BONE CHAR FOR THE REMOVAL OF PHOSPHATE

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JULY 2021

ABSTRACT

Magnetized bone char was utilized in the removal of phosphate from water by adsorption process. Batch method was employed the effect of initial concentration at various time of the adsorption process. The experimental data was investigated by pseudo and pseudo second order kinetic models to explain the mechanism of the sorption process. The equilibrium data was also fitted into different isotherm models including Freundlich and Langmuir.

The result showed that the adsorption was best described by the Freundlich isotherm while the Kinetics data was best explained by the pseudo first and second order model. The maximum adsorption capacity of unmodified bone char was 12.53 mg/g. The data obtained also indicates that magnetized bone char could serve as a low cost and alternative for the effective removal of phosphate from water.

1.0

INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Water pollution maybe defined as the alteration in the physical, chemical and biological characteristics of water which may cause harmful effects on human and aquatic life.(Khatun, 2017)

SOURCES OF WATER POLLUTION

Water pollution in Nigeria according to (Owa, 2013) arises from various activities, among which are:

- i. Sewage leakages
- ii. High population density
- iii. Oil spillage
- iv. Menace of Nipa palm and water hyacinth
- v. Industrial waste dumped into our waters
- vi. Pollution ground waters through drilling activities
- vii. Flooding during rainy season which carries waste deposit into our waters
- viii. Building lavatories and visionaries over running water or even the sea as it the practice in some riverine areas
- ix. Radioisotopes
- x. Heavy metals
- xi. Combustion
- xii. Toxic waste disposal at sea
- xiii. Mineral processing plant (e.g coal production)
- xiv. Eroded sediments
- xv. Deforestation
- xvi. Mining
- xvii. Littering
- xviii. Pesticides
- xix. Herbicides and fertilizers
- xx. Failing septic system
- xxi. House hold chemicals
- xxii. Animal wastes.

POINT SOURCE: It is a well-defined source that emits pollutants or effluents directly into different water bodies of fresh water. Domestic and industrial waste are examples of this type.

NON-POINT SOURCE: They are scattered or spread over large areas. It is a much bigger problem because it occurs when rainfall, snowfall, or irrigation runs over land or through the ground and picks up pollutants and deposits them in bodies of water.

Point source and non-point source pollution cause serious problems:

- Photosynthesis in aquatic plants may be disrupted affecting ecosystems that depend on these plants;
- Terrestrial and aquatic plants and trees may absorb pollutants from water;
- Plants and trees may be killed by mud from construction sites and clay;
- Plants and trees may be killed by herbicides in water and these are chemicals which are most harmful to plants and forest tree species.(Viman et al,2010)

METHODS FOR WASTE WATER TREATMENT:

The various methods available for the treatment of hazardous waste was described by (Turker et al, 2011).

- Physical method:** physical treatment process include gravity separation, phase change system such as Air stream stripping of volatile from liquid waste, adsorption, reverse osmosis, ion exchange, electro dialysis.
- Chemical method:** chemical methods usually aimed at transforming the hazardous waste into less hazardous substances using techniques such as pH neutralization, oxidation or reduction and precipitation.
- Biological methods:** biological treatment method use microorganisms to degrade organic pollutant in waste stream.
- Thermal methods:** thermal destruction process that are commonly used include incineration and pyrolysis incineration is becoming more preferred option. In pyrolysis, the waste material is heated in the absence of oxygen to bring about chemical decomposition.
- Fixation/immobilization/stabilization techniques** involve the dewatering of waste and solidifying the remaining material by mixing it with stabilizing agent such as Portland cement or pozzolanic material, or vitrifying it to create a glassy substance. For hazardous inorganic sledges, solidification process is used.

ADSORPTION: Adsorption is the process of transferring material from a fluid phase to a solid state. Adsorption is also a separation process in which some materials, (adsorbate) is concentrated from a bulk vapor or liquid phase on to the surface of a porous solid (adsorbent). Some common examples of adsorption are the silica gel packets to absorb moisture from packaged electronic or optical equipment, and carbon filter to deodorize drinking water (Gawande et al, 2017).

ADSORPTION ISOTHERM MODELS: The different adsorption isotherms was described by (Wang and Guo,2020).

Isotherm refers to the relationship between the equilibrium adsorbate concentrations in the liquid-phase and the equilibrium adsorption amount on the solid-phase at a certain temperature.

- Linear model:** The linear isotherm model has been used to represent the partition of adsorbates between solid and liquid phases. The linear model (Henry's law) has the following form:

$$q_e = KC_e \quad (1)$$

Where q_e ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) and c_e ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) are adsorbed amount and adsorbate concentrations at equilibrium, K ($\text{L}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) is the partition coefficient.

Based on the deduction of the linear model, the linear model represents the condition that the coverage ratio of the adsorption sites is low. Therefore, the linear model can represent the monolayer adsorption at low initial adsorbate concentrations C_0 . It was suggested that Langmuir model is approximated to Henry's law when the pressure is low in the adsorption of gas on solid, which was similar with our results.

b. Freundlich isotherm: The Freundlich model is used to represent nonlinear adsorption phenomenon. It is one of the most widely used isotherm in adsorption. The linear and nonlinear forms of the Freundlich model is given by the following equations:

$$q_e = K_f C_e^{1/n} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Log } q_e = \text{log } K_f + 1/n \text{ log } C_e \quad (3)$$

where K_f ($\text{L}^{1/n}\cdot\text{mg}^{1-1/n}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) and n are constants, the Freundlich model will reduce to the linear model when $n=1$.

The nonlinear Freundlich model can be solved by nonlinear regression analysis. It is easily to be solved by plotting $\text{log } q_e$ versus $\text{log } C_e$. However, the propagated errors are generated in the linearization process, which lead to the inaccurate estimations of parameters. In this paper, the nonlinear method is recommended in the calculation of the parameters. The Freundlich model has been regarded as an empirical equation without physical meaning. In many published papers, the Freundlich isotherm was applied to represent the multi-layer adsorption on heterogeneous surfaces.

c. Redlich-Peterson (R-P): The R-P model is an empirical hybrid model of the Langmuir and Freundlich models, which has been frequently applied in the homogeneous or heterogeneous adsorption processes. The R-P isotherm model can be described by Eq 4;

$$q_e = \frac{K_{RP} C_e}{1 + a_{RP} C_e^g} \quad (4)$$

Where K_{RP} ($\text{L}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) and a_{RP} ($\text{L}^g\cdot\text{mg}^{-g}$) are constants, g is the exponent ($0 \leq g \leq 1$). We can see from Eq. (4) that g equals to 1, the R-P model reduces to the Langmuir model and when g equals 0 or C_e approaches to 0, it will reduce to the linear model. In addition, if C_e approaches to infinite, $q_e \approx (K_{RP}/a_{RP}) C_e^{(1-g)}$, which reduces to the Freundlich model.

d. Temkin isotherm: The Temkin model presumes that adsorption is a multi-layer process. Extremely high and low concentrations values of the adsorbate in liquid phase are ignored. Derivation of the statistical mechanical expression for the Temkin isotherm and substituted the derived equation into the Clapeyron-Clausius equation, confirmed that the differential heat of adsorption was linear decreased with increasing coverage. The Temkin model is presented by Eq. (5);

$$q_e = \frac{RT}{b} \ln (AC_e) \quad (5)$$

Where A (L.g⁻¹) and b (j.mol⁻¹) are the constants.

- e. **Langmuir isotherm:** The most commonly applied Langmuir isotherm was raised to represent the gas-solid adsorption. The nonlinear and linear Langmuir models are presented as following;

$$q_e = \frac{q_m K_L C_e}{1 + K_L C_e} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{C_e}{q_e} + \frac{1}{K_L q_m} \quad (7)$$

Where K_L (L.mg⁻¹) is the ratio of the adsorption rate and desorption rate, q_m (mg.g⁻¹) is the maximum adsorption capacity estimated by the Langmuir model.

Eq. 6 is solved by the nonlinear regression method. Plotting C_e/q_e versus C_e can solve the linearized Langmuir model Eq. (7)

- f. **BET model:** BET model was proposed to represent adsorption of gas to multimolecular layers. It is a theoretical multi-layer physical adsorption model. It has been applied for calculation the specific areas and the pore size distribution of the porous materials. The basic presumptions of BET isotherm are that the adsorption is multi-layer homogeneous adsorption, the adsorption energy in the first layer is different with other layers, and for each layer, the adsorption rate equals to the desorption rate. The application of the BET isotherm in liquid-solid systems is presented in Eq. (8)

$$q_e = \frac{q_{mBET} K_{BET1} C_e [1 - (n_{BET} + 1)(K_{BET2} C_e)^{n_{BET}} + n_{BET} (K_{BET2} C_e)^{n_{BET} + 1}]}{(1 - K_{BET2} C_e) [1 + (\frac{K_{BET1}}{K_{BET2}} - 1) K_{BET2} C_e - (\frac{K_{BET1}}{K_{BET2}}) (K_{BET2} C_e)^{n_{BET} + 1}]} \quad (8)$$

ADSORPTION KINETIC MODELS: The different kinetic models was described by (Wang and Guo, 2020).

- a. **Pseudo-first-order (PFO) model:** The differential form of the PFO model is described by Eq. (9);

$$\frac{dq_t}{dt} = k_1 (q_e - q_t) \quad (9)$$

Integrating Eq. (9) for the conditions of q_e = 0 yields:

$$q_t = q_e (1 - e^{-k_1 t}) \quad (10)$$

The linearized form of the PFO model is presented as follows;

$$\ln (q_e - q_t) = \ln q_e - k_1 t \quad (11)$$

Eq. (11) has been frequently used to fit the kinetics data and to calculate the parameters q_e and k₁, by plotting ln (q_e-q_t) vs. t. However, the linearization process may be cause in accurate estimations of the parameters.

The PFO parameter q_e is the equilibrium adsorption amount estimated by the PFO model. It is reported that the PFO model was theoretically consistent and equaled to the linear driving (LDF) model, when the adsorption isotherm could be represented by the linear model (12).

$$q = KC_e^e \quad (12)$$

The PFO parameter k_1 has been used frequently to describe how fast the adsorption equilibrium is achieved. However, as shown in Eq. (9), the adsorption rate dq_t/dt is related to both k_1 and $(q_e - q_t)$. Small value k_1 and big value of $(q_e - q_t)$ could be obtained when the adsorption is slow. Therefore, it is more precise to calculate the PFO rate by Eq. (13), instead of describing the adsorption rate by comparing the values of k_1 .

$$\text{PFO rate} = k_1(q_e - q_t) \quad (13)$$

- b. Pseudo-second-order (PSO) model:** The PSO model Eq. (14) was firstly applied to model the adsorption of lead onto peat. Then the PSO model was widely adopted to describe the adsorption processes. Most published papers used the PSO model to predict the adsorption experimental data and to calculate the adsorption rate constants.

$$\frac{dq_t}{dt} = k_2(q_e - q_t)^2 \quad (14)$$

The integrated PSO model is described as following:

$$q_t = \frac{q_e^2 k_2 t}{1 + q_e k_2 t} \quad (15)$$

In order to calculate the model parameters, the nonlinear PSO model is always transformed to the linear form Eq. (16)

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e} \quad (16)$$

The linearization of the PSO model changes the weight of q_t and introduces propagated errors, which leads to the inaccurate calculations of the model parameters. Similar with the PFO rate constant k_1 , the PSO rate constant k_2 is also used to describe the rate of adsorption equilibrium. But the adsorption rate dq_t/dt is related to both k_2 and $(q_e - q_t)^2$. Thus, it is more precise to calculate the PSO rate by Eq. (17).

$$\text{PSO rate} = k_2 (q_e - q_t)^2 \quad (17)$$

- c. Mixed-order (MO) model:** The mixed-order (MO) model has the following form;

$$\frac{dq_t}{dt} = k_1 (q_e - q_t) + k_2 (q_e - q_t)^2 \quad (18)$$

The PFO and PSO rate of MO model can be calculated by Eqs. (19) and (20).

$$\text{PFO rate}' = k'_1 (q_e - q_t) \quad (19)$$

$$\text{PFO rate}' = k'_2 (q_e - q_t)^2 \quad (20)$$

In most cases, the PFO rate and PSO rate describe the diffusion step and the step of adsorption on active sites, respectively. In addition, the MO model represents the overall adsorption process.

d. Elovich model: The basic assumptions of the Elovich model were

1. The activation energy increased with adsorption time and
2. The surface of the adsorbent was heterogeneous.

The Elovich model is an empirical model without definite physical meanings. It is commonly used to model the chemisorption of gas onto solid. The Elovich model has been described by Eq. (21):

$$\frac{dq_t}{dt} = ae^{-bq_t} \quad (21)$$

Integrating Eq. (21) for the condition of $q_0 = 0$ yields:

$$q_t = \frac{1}{b} \ln(1 + abt) \quad (22)$$

Eq. (22) is a nonlinear equation, which can be solved by the nonlinear least square regression method (plot q_t versus t) or by the linear method (plot q_t versus $\ln(1 + abt)$). However, the nonlinear method is more complex than the linear method needs to give the appropriate initial values of ab , which is difficult for researchers simplified Eq. (22) with the assumption of $abt \gg 1$:

$$q_t = \frac{1}{b} \ln(ab) + \frac{1}{b} \ln(t) \quad (23)$$

Plotting q_t versus $\ln(t)$ can solve Eq. (23) by linear regression method. In the past decade, the Elovich model has been used to represent the adsorption of liquid-solid systems.

1.1.1. BACKGROUND OF PROBLEM

Phosphate is crucial in water contamination. Eutrophication, which is the overgrowth of algae, is often caused by excess discharge of phosphorus in water and results in deterioration of water quality. Ways in which phosphate is released into aquatic environment are by various human activities such as mining, industrial and agricultural utilization (Yao et al, 2017). In humans, an increase in serum P level for patients may lead to the early progression of chronic kidney disease. Hence, hyperphosphatemia which is the late indicator of phosphorus retention, can increase some potential risks regarding cardiovascular morbidity and mortality in patients undergoing hemodialysis (Chun-Chieh, 2019). Pollution by phosphate is ever increasing and therefore, there is an urgent demand to take highly effective, reliable and

economical methods for efficient phosphate removal (Yao et al, 2017). So, the removal of phosphate ion from water can be an effective method for the control of eutrophication in natural water. (Shi et al, 2011). For the removal of phosphate, various techniques have been used successfully such as chemical precipitation with lime, alum and iron salts. The technique is effective for phosphate removal, however there are problems of sludge handling, its disposal and neutralization of the effluent. Adsorptive removal of phosphate from aqueous solution using various adsorbents have been studied by various investigations (Kumar et al, 2010). Adsorption is one of the techniques, which is comparatively more useful and economical for removal because of low cost and easily available materials in waste water and it has been investigated widely in recent years (Ragheb,2013). Activated carbon is the most common adsorbent used for this purpose of treating waste water. Although, carbonaceous porous materials (i.e biochar and activated carbon) have been widely applied for environmental remediation, especially water treatment, their applications in the elimination of phosphate from water might be limited to some extent. This is because they exhibit a relatively low adsorption capacity to phosphates. The low adsorption capacity resulted from the negligible role of pore filling in the adsorption mechanism of phosphate onto porous materials. (Xing-Han et al, 2019). To improve the adsorption capacity of phosphate, some scholars have developed the functionalized or modified adsorbents that exhibited the abundant adsorption sites on their external surface. Such adsorbents include magnetic adsorbents and it is one of the most efficient technical, and economical methods for treating water. These adsorbents have magnetic properties and by using an external magnetic field, can be easily separated from solutions (Mohammed and Moeinpour, 2017). Magnetically activated carbon are prepared mainly by coprecipitation of the magnetic material with activated carbon or by impregnation of the activated carbon with a salt of iron, cobalt or nickel and further heating at higher temperatures forming the magnetic material that is impregnated in the carbon matrix (Pascal et al, 2020). In this research, cow bone which is a source of carbon biomass was successfully prepared by heating in the conventional heating furnace and it was used for the proposed magnetically activated carbon (MAC). Nickel chloride and Zinc chloride was used added to the bone char to produce the MAC.

1.1.2. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Presence of phosphate causes contamination in water by eutrophication which results in deterioration of water quality. To reduce eutrophication in water, phosphate has to be removed. This can be done by various techniques such as chemical precipitation and adsorption. Adsorption is one of the technique which is more useful and economic for removal because of its low cost and easily available material. Adsorption using carbonaceous porous materials have been widely used but their application for the removal of phosphate is limited because they have a relatively low adsorptive capacity to phosphate. In this work, MAC has been prepared using Nickel chloride (NiCl_2) and Zinc chloride (NiCl_2) to increase the pore size and surface area to improve adsorptive capacity of the biochar.

1.1.3. JUSTIFICATION OF WORK

- There is very limited studies of magnetized bone char for the removal of phosphate.
- Batch adsorption studies has been done for the removal of phosphate with magnetized bone char.

1.1.4. SCOPE OF WORK

This work is centered on developing a biochar with large pore size and surface area to increase its adsorptive capacity. This biochar will be developed from cow bone. The MAC will be developed by mixing the bone char with Zinc chloride and Nickel chloride. Then, batch sorption studies of bone char will be carried out using potassium dihydrogen phosphate. Thermodynamic and kinetic study will be determined.

1.1.5. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

AIM: To develop magnetized bone char for the removal of phosphate from aqueous solution.

OBJECTIVES: To achieve this aim the following objectives were set;

- Prepare bone char
- Prepare magnetized bone char
- Carry out batch sorption studies of bone char using potassium dihydrogen phosphate
- Determine kinetic and thermodynamics study

1.2 LITERATURE REVIEW

- Safaa M. Ragheb (2013) used fly ash and slag as a potential adsorbent for the removal of phosphate, heavy metals and organic pollutants in wastewater treatment.
- Sicong Yao et al (2017) prepared activated carbon from sewage sludge by chemical activation with pyrolusite to develop an efficient adsorbent for phosphate removal.
- SHI Zhong-liang et al (2011) synthesized activated carbon by loading it with iron oxide for the removal of phosphate.
- Predeep Kumar et al (2010) developed activated carbon from coir pith for the removal of phosphates from aqueous solution .
- Mohammad H. Tarmahi and Farid Moeinpour (2017) evaluated the efficiency of polyaniline/Ni_{0.5}Zn_{0.5}Fe₂O₄ magnetic nanocomposite in removing phosphate from aqueous environments.

- Chun-Chieh Fu et al (2019) developed polyaminated-grafted Fe₃O₄@ chitosan core shell magnetic particles to show the adsorption mechanism towards phosphate and the recovery of the used particles under an applied magnetic field.
- Pascal S. Thue et al (2020) synthesized new nanomagnetic activated carbon material with high magnetization and high surface area in a single pyrolysis step.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 MATERIALS

- Cow bone
- Nickel chloride
- Zinc chloride
- Hydrochloric acid
- Distilled water
- Potassium dihydrogen phosphate
- Sodium chloride
- Ammonium molybdate
- Sodium sulphide
- Sulfuric acid
- 250ml conical flask
- 250ml beakers
- 1000ml volumetric flask
- 100ml volumetric flask
- 25ml volumetric flask
- 50ml measuring cylinder

- 10ml measuring cylinder
- Funnels
- Rotating shaker
- Filter papers
- Crucible
- Condenser

2.2. METHODOLOGY

2.2.1. PREPARATION OF ADSORBENT (BONE CHAR)

Cow bone was washed thoroughly and dried. After drying, it was carbonized in a muffle furnace at 300°C. After carbonizing, it was crushed to powder form.

2.2.2. PREPARATION OF MAGNETIZED BONE CHAR

Preparation of magnetic activated bone char was carried out according to the method described by (Pascal et al, 2020).

The MAC was prepared by a single-step procedure described as following; First, 100g of the powder of bone char was mixed with 1g of $ZrCl_2$ and 2g of $NiCl_2$. During the mixing, 70ml of water was added to optimize the mixing and allow the formation of a paste. Then it was introduced in a muffle furnace at 600°C for 30mins. Then, the furnace was shut down. However, the inert condition was maintained until the temperature was less than 200°C. After cooling, the samples were partially leached-out using a 0.1 M HCl solution under a reflux system for 60mins to maintain the Ni compounds embedded in the carbon matrix, and try to eliminate the maximum of Zn compounds to enlarge the pores. After the leaching, the samples were exhaustively washed with water until the pH of the washing water attains the pH of deionized water. The sample was furtherly dried at 105°C in oven.

2.2.3. PREPARATION OF ADSORBATE

Preparation of the adsorbate was carried out according the method described by (Safaa, 2013).

Simulated stock solution of phosphate ions (ie.1000mg/l) was prepared in a 1000ml volumetric flask by dissolving 0.2195g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in distilled water.

2.2.4. PREPARATION OF DIFFERENT PHOSPHATE SOLUTIONS

Preparation of different phosphate solutions was carried out according to the method described by (Safaa, 2013).

Stock solution of potassium dihydrogen phosphate was further diluted with distilled water to desired concentrations of 10mg/l, 20mg/l, 30mg/l, 50mg/l, 100mg/l and 500mg/l.

2.2.5. BATCH ADSORPTION STUDIES

Batch adsorption studies was carried out according to method described by (Safaa, 2013).

Batch adsorption experiments were carried out by shaking series of bottles containing various amounts of each low cost adsorbent (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1g) which was equilibrated with 50ml Of the phosphate ion solution of a known concentrations (10, 20, 30 ,50 ,100 and 500mg/l) at a speed of 200 rpm at room temperature for a known period (10, 20, 30, 40, 50 and 60 mins) of time with a rotary shaker.

2.2.6. DEVELOPMENT OF PHOSPHATE COLOUR

The molybdate spectrophotometric method was used to detect residual phosphate concentration (Mahadey et al, 2017).

1ml of the sample, 1ml of sodium sulphide, 3ml of sulphuric acid and 0.5ml of ammonium molybdate was added to a 25ml volumetric flask and filled to the mark with distilled water.

2.2.7. ADSORPTION MODELS OF KINETICS AND ISOTHERMS

Adsorption models of kinetics and isotherms were analysed using “mistakes and inconsistencies regarding adsorption of contaminants from solution” (Tran, 2017).

The kinetic adsorption models of pseudo-first-order, pseudo-second-order, elovich, intra-particle were employed to analyse the obtained data.

The equilibrium data were fitted with the Freundlich, Langmuir and Temkin isotherm models.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. EFFECT OF ADSORBENT DOSAGE

The variation in % adsorption of phosphate ion (PO_4^{3-}) from aqueous solution with increasing adsorbent dosage is shown in figure 1. At a constant initial concentration of 50mg/L, a constant time (60mins) and temperature (27°C), the rate of adsorption was found to have no significant change in adsorbent dosage (0.2-1.0g) for the metal ions studied. The MAC highest adsorbent dose removed 99.83578% of PO_4^{3-} .

Figure 1: Effect of adsorbent dosage on the percentage of PO_4^{3-} removal using MAC.

3.2. ADSORPTION KINETICS

In this study, kinetic models and the diffusion model were used to describe the metal ion adsorption process on the adsorbents. The non-linearized forms of pseudo-first-order, pseudo-second-order, Elovich are expressed in equation 24, 25 and 26 respectively. The linear form of the diffusion model is given in equation 27.

$$q_t = q_e(1 - e^{-k_1 t}) \quad (24)$$

$$q_t = \frac{q_e^2 k_2 t}{1 + k_2 q_e t} \quad (25)$$

$$q_t = \frac{1}{\beta} \ln(1 + \alpha \beta t) \quad (26)$$

$$q_t = k_p \sqrt{t} + C \quad (27)$$

where K_1 (min^{-1}), K_2 ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$), α ($\text{mg/m} \times \text{min}$), and K_p ($\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{min}^{1/2}$) are the rate constants of pseudo-first-order, pseudo-second-order, Elovich and intra-particle diffusion models, respectively; q_e and q_t are the amounts of adsorbate uptake per mass of the adsorbents at equilibrium and any time t (min), respectively; and C (mg/g) is a constant associated with the thickness of the boundary layer, where a higher value of C corresponds to a greater effect on the limiting boundary layer.

The relative parameters of the pseudo-first order, pseudo second-order, Elovich and intraparticle diffusion models are shown in Table 1. According to the coefficient of determination (R^2) and chi-square (χ^2), it can be concluded that the experimental data were adequately described by pseudo-first-order model ($R^2 = 1$ and $\chi^2 = 0.335$) than the others such as the pseudo-second-order model ($R^2 = 0.999$ and $\chi^2 = 0.579$), Elovich model ($R^2 = 0.904$ and $\chi^2 = 0.045$). The better fit of experimental data with the pseudo-first-order model suggest that one metal ion is sorbed onto one sorption site on the adsorbent surface as illustrated in Eq. (28).

Where A represent an unoccupied sorption site on the surface of the adsorbent and K_1 is the pseudo-first – order rate constant ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$).

Although, the pseudo first order model can describe adsorption kinetic experimental data, it does not reveal the adsorption mechanisms. In contrast, the intra-particle diffusion is relevant for identifying the adsorption pathways, adsorption mechanisms and predicting the rate determining step. According to the intra-particle diffusion model, (i) sorption process is controlled by intra-particle diffusion if the plot of q_t against $t_{1/2}$ should be linear (ii) intra-particle diffusion is the rate determining step if the lines do not deviate from the origin and (iii) it is a multi- step adsorption process if the data has two or more slopes .

Table 1: Kinetic parameters for PO_4^{3-} adsorption onto MAC

Pseudo-first-order model				Pseudo-second-order model				Elovich model			
$q_{e,cal}$	K_1	R^2	χ^2	$q_{e,cal}$	K_2	R^2	χ^2	β	A	R^2	χ^2
0.55	0.05	1	0.335	1.034	0.022	0.999	0.579	11.7	0.729	0.904	0.045

Table 2: Intraparticle parameters for PO_4^{3-} adsorption onto MAC at room

K_p (mg/gm ^{0.5})	Intercept(C)	R^2	χ^2
0.039	0.2469	1	0.058

3.3. ADSORPTION ISOTHERM

In this study, the Langmuir (Eq. (29)) and Freundlich (Eq. (30)) models were employed to describe the adsorptive behaviour of PO_4^{3-} ion. To minimize the respective error functions, the non-linear optimization techniques was applied for calculating the adsorption parameters from these models.

$$Q_e = \frac{Q_{max}K_L C_e}{1 + K_L C_e} \quad (12)$$

$$q_e = K_F C_e^n \quad (13)$$

Where C_e (mg/L) and q_e (mg/g) are obtained from Eq. (1); q_m (mg/g) is the maximum saturated monolayer adsorption capacity of an adsorbent; K_L (mg/L) is the Langmuir constant related to affinity between and adsorbent and adsorbate, K_F (mg/g)/(mg/L)ⁿ is the Freundlich constant which characterizes the strength of adsorption; n(dimensionless) is adsorption intensity.

The parameters of adsorption models are listed in Table 3 and Table 4. The values of R^2 and χ^2 for the Freundlich (1 and 5.408) best describe the experimental equilibrium data. Furthermore, n value is less than unity for MAC. Isotherms with $n > 1$ are classified as unfavourable and favourable with $n < 1$. The Temkin isotherm also showed a good fit to experimental data on the basis of determination coefficient ($R^2=1$). The values of heat of adsorption ($B= 26.345\text{J/mol}$) and binding constant ($K= 13.381$)

Table 3: Freundlich and Langmuir isotherm model parameters for PO_4^{3-} ion adsorption by MAC

Freundlich isotherm				Langmuir isotherm			
K_f	n	R^2	χ^2	q_m	K_L	R^2	χ^2
2.495	0	1	5.408	201.58	1617.86	1	5.418

TABLE 4: Temkin isotherm parameters

Temkin isotherm			
B	K	R^2	χ^2
26.345	13.381	1	5.2426

Figure 2: Adsorption isotherm

Table 5: Showing Qmax and system types of different works compared to the current study.

Adsorbent	Qmax	System type	Reference
Tucuma MAC	199.3mg/g	Batch sorption process	Pascal et al, 2020
Iron oxide activated carbon	98.39mg/g	Batch sorption process	Shi et al, 2011
Polyaniline/ $\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ magnetic nanocomposite	85.4mg/g	Batch sorption process	Mohammad and Moeinpour, 2017
Bone MAC	201.58mg/g	Batch sorption process	Present study

CONCLUSION

The magnetized bone char is seen to be highly effective to remove phosphate from water. The equilibrium data analysed showed that the experimental data of the adsorption isotherm follows the Freundlich model and Pseudo-first order kinetic model. Temkin isotherm was found to represent the adsorption equilibrium data well. The magnetized bone char could serve as an alternative to other absorbents for the removal of phosphate.

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